

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part—XIII : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of Thiazolidinones and Their Derivatives Possessing Thiadiazole, Oxadiazole and Isothiazole Moieties

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Several thiazolidinones, arylidene thiazolidinones and their dibromides, dimethylaminomethyl thiazolidinones and sulphonamidophenylazo compounds possessing thiadiazole, oxadiazole and isothiazole moieties have been synthesised from the respective thioureas with monochloroacetic acid. The structures of the compounds have been confirmed from spectral data. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the compounds have been evaluated.

THE synthesis of thiazolidinone compounds possessing heterocyclic moieties such as thiazole, benzothiazole, pyridine and several other aromatic systems have been reported by us¹. Most of these compounds possess significant bactericidal and fungicidal activities. Although the synthesis and antimicrobial² activities of thiadiazole³, oxadiazole⁴ and isothiazole⁵ compounds are well documented, the thiazolidinone derivatives possessing these nuclei are little known⁶. Since 4-thiazolidinone itself is pharmacologically active the presence of both the moieties in one compound may augment the potency. Therefore, in continuation of our earlier work on thiazolidinones several thiadiazolylimino, oxadiazolylimino and isothiazolyliminothiazolidinone derivatives have been synthesised with a view of evaluating their antimicrobial activities.

In the present study, 2-(5-arylthiadiazolylimino-2)-4-thiazolidinones (IIa-e), 2-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazolylimino-2)-4-thiazolidinones (IIf-j) and 2-(5-phenylisothiazolylimino-2)-4-thiazolidinone (IIk) were synthesised by the reaction of the respective thioureas (I) with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in alcohol. These thioureas were prepared by the reaction of respective amines with benzoylthiocyanate with the amine and subsequent hydrolysis of the resulting product. The ir of the thiazolidinone (IIa) gave a weak band at 2905 cm⁻¹ and a strong sharp band at 1750 cm⁻¹ corresponding to -CH₂- and >C=O stretch, respectively, whereas its benzylidene derivative (IIIa) gave a strong sharp band at 1705 cm⁻¹ for carbonyl and the band in the region of 2900 cm⁻¹ was absent. The bathochromic shift for the carbonyl absorption is due to conjugation with exomethylene group. Similarly the ¹H nmr spectrum of the thiazolidinone (IIa) furnished a two proton singlet at

δ 4.25 and another one proton singlet at δ 6.90 corresponding to methylene of thiazolidinone and thiadiazole ring C-5 proton, respectively. Besides these, another broad peak centred at δ 5.6 appeared corresponding to -NH- proton which underwent exchange after shaking with D₂O and the peak disappeared. The peak at δ 4.25 was absent on its benzylidene derivative (IIIa). It gave two singlets at δ 6.1 and δ 7.00, each representing one proton corresponding to methine and thiadiazole ring protons, respectively. Since bromine augments the antimicrobial activities⁶, the arylidene compounds (II) were brominated to dibromo derivative (IV). The structures of these bromo derivatives were also confirmed from spectral studies. The ir of 2-(1,3,4-thiadiazolylimino-2)-5-bromo-5-(α-bromo benzyl)-4-thiazolidinone (IVa) gave a sharp peak at 1730 cm⁻¹ corresponding to carbonyl absorption. Such hypsochromic shift from the benzylidene derivative (IIIa) was due to inhibition of conjugation arising out of saturation. Moreover, the nmr of the dibromo compound furnished a singlet at δ 3.1 corresponding to benzylic proton besides the thiadiazole and aromatic ring protons which appeared at δ 7.0 and δ 7.45, respectively. The upfield shift in the methine proton of the benzylidene compound is due to saturation of the double bond. Besides these, several aminomethyl derivatives (V) and sulphonamido compounds (VI) were synthesised from the thiazolidinones for evaluation of such properties.

Antimicrobial activities : The preliminary screening for the fungicidal and bactericidal activities of the compounds were made on Sabouraud's broth medium and agar plate techniques, respectively. The tests were done on two soil fungi (*A. niger* and *C. albican*) and two bacteria (*S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*). Chloromycetin was used as the standard

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1. NH_4CNS , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}$, acetone ; 2. $\text{Cl}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{COOH}$, NaOAc , EtOH ; 3. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHO}$, NaOAc , AcOH ; 4. Br_2 , AcOH ;
 5. NaNO_2 , HCl , sulphanilamide ; 6. Secondary amine, paraformaldehyde, HCl and EtOH .

for bacterial activities and the size of the zone was 50 mm. The minimum inhibitory concentration for Diethane M-45 used as the standard for fungicidal activity evaluation was found to be 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ for both the fungi. The test results reveal that the thiazolidinone derivatives possessing isothiazolyl and thiadiazolyl moieties are more potent than the oxadiazolyl derivatives but none of the compounds show a potency comparable to the standards.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra of the compounds were taken on KBr disc in Perkin Elmer model 293 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra of the compounds were recorded in CDCl_3 solution using TMS as internal standard ($\delta=0$ ppm) and recorded on Varian HA-60 spectrometer.

2-Amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole was prepared by the reaction of thiasemicarbazide and formic acid according to Lauer *et al*⁷, whereas the 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were prepared by the oxidative cyclization of benzylidene thiasemicarbazones with hydrated FeCl_3 . The m.p.s of 2-amino, 2-amino-5-phenyl, 2-amino-5-chlorophenyl, 2-amino-5-anisyl and 2-amino-5-*p*-nitrophenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were 195, 218, 197 and 230°, respectively. Similarly 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared by the oxidative cyclisation of arylidene semicarbazones in bromine and acetic acid in

presence of anhydrous sodium acetate⁹. The m.p.s of 2-amino-5-phenyl, 2-amino-5-*p*-chlorophenyl, 2-amino-5-*p*-anisyl and 2-amino-5-*p*-nitrophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were 238, 268, 252 and 250°, respectively. 5-Amino-3-phenylisothiazole was prepared by the oxidative cyclization of β -iminophenyl thio-propionamide with iodine in presence of K_2CO_3 , m.p. 161° (lit¹⁰, m.p. 161°).

*N*₁-(1,3,4-Thiadiazolyl-2)thiourea (Ia) : To a solution of ammonium thiocyanate (7.6 g ; 0.1 M) in acetone (20 ml) in a three necked flask provided with a reflux condenser was added benzoyl chloride (12 ml) dropwise with stirring. It was refluxed for 30 min after which 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (5 g ; 0.05 M) in acetone (75 ml) was added with stirring during 15 min. The benzoyl derivative of the thiourea obtained as dark brown precipitate was filtered and dissolved in 10% NaOH solution by boiling for 15 min. It was filtered to remove the little insoluble material. After cooling, the solution was acidified with conc. HCl during which a pale yellow precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol-acetone (2 : 1) mixture, m.p. 204°, yield 5.2 g (63%). (Found : S, 39.84 ; N, 34.90. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ requires S, 40 ; N, 35%).

*N*₁-(5-Phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2)thiourea (If) : It was prepared from ammonium thiocyanate (1.5 g), benzoyl chloride (6 ml) and 5-phenyl-2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2.20 g) by following the above procedure

and finally recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 201°, yield 1.5 g (56%). (Found: S, 14.41. C₉H₈N₄SO requires S, 14.54%).

*N*₁-(3-Phenylisothiazolyl-5)thiourea (Ik): This was prepared from 5-amino-3-phenylisothiazole and benzoylthiocyanate by following the general procedure, m.p. 142°, yield 50%. (Found: S, 27.16. C₁₀H₉N₃S₂ requires S, 27.23%).

2-(1,3,4-Thiadiazolylimino-2)-4-thiazolidinone (IIa): A mixture of *N*₁-(1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-2)thiourea (1.6 g), monochloroacetic acid (0.95 g) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.5 g) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The solvent was distilled off and the residue was filtered after trituration with water. It was washed several times with cold water to make it free from sodium acetate, dried and recrystallised from ethanol as colourless plates, m.p. 211°, yield 1.3 g (70%). (Found: S, 31.87. C₈H₄N₄S₂O requires S, 32%); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) 3345 (broad, -NH-), 2905 (-CH₂- stretch), 1750 (C=O), 1965 (C=N); NMR: δ 4.25 (s, 2H, -CH₂-), 5.6 (broad singlet, -NH-, exchanged with D₂O), 6.90 (s, 1H, thiadiazole ring proton).

2-(5-Phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolylimino-2)-4-thiazolidinone (IIb): This was prepared in 75% yield by taking a mixture of 5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2-thiourea (1.1 g), monochloroacetic acid (0.5 g) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.25 g) and finally recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 197°, yield 0.8 g (75%). (Found: S, 12.08. C₁₁H₈N₄SO₂ requires S, 12.30%); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) 3340 (broad, -NH-), 2900 (-CH₂- stretch), 1750 (C=O), 1690 (C=N).

2-(3-Phenylisothiazolylimino-5)-4-thiazolidinone (IIc): This was prepared by following the general work up procedure by taking isothiazolylthiourea (1.16 g) and monochloroacetic acid (0.5 g) and other required reagents. Colourless plates, m.p. 206°, yield 0.8 g (60%), (Found: S, 23.32. C₁₁H₉N₃S₂O requires S, 23.26%).

2-(1,3,4-Thiazolylimino-2)-5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone (IIIa): The thiazolidinone (IIa) (1 g) and benzaldehyde (0.5 ml) in ethanol (20 ml) with 2 drops of piperidine was refluxed for 4 hr and cooled to room temperature during which yellow crystalline flakes separated, m.p. 200°, yield 60%. (Found: S, 22.12. C₁₂H₈N₄S₂O requires S, 22.22%); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) 3350 (broad, -NH-), 1705 (C=O), 1690 (C=N); NMR: δ 4.2 (broad, 1H, -NH- exchanged with D₂O), 6.1 (s, 1H, -CH-), 7.0 (s, 1H thiadiazole C₅ proton), 7.3 (m, 5H, aromatic protons).

2-(1,3,4-Thiadiazolylimino-2)-5-bromo-5-(α -bromobenzyl)-4-thiazolidinone (IVa): The benzylidene derivative (IIIa) (0.3 g) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and bromine (0.3 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added dropwise at 0° and kept overnight. The orange crystals separated were filtered, washed with ether and dried, m.p. 200°, yield 30%. (Found: Br, 35.60. C₁₂H₈N₄S₂OBr₂ requires Br, 35.71%); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) 3400 (broad -NH-), 1730 (C=O), 1600 (C=N); NMR: δ 3.1 (s, -CH-, 1H), 4.6 (s, broad, -NH-, 1H, exchanged with D₂O), 7.0 (s, 1H, thiadiazole C-5 proton), 7.45 (m, 5H, aromatic protons).

The analytical data and antimicrobial test results of the thioureas and thiazolidinones and benzylidene derivatives and their dibromides have been presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Sulphonamidophenylazo derivatives V from II: Sulphanilamide (0.005 mole) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and water (25 ml) was diazotised with NaNO₂ (0.25 g in 30 ml of water) in an ice bath. The diazo solution thus prepared was added gradually with stirring to a previously cooled solution of thiazolidinone (II) (0.005 M). The orange azo dyes separated were filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-(1,3,4-Thiadiazolylimino-2)-5-dimethylaminoethyl-4-thiazolidinone (VIa): A mixture of thiazoli-

TABLE 1

Compound	Thioureas (I)					Thiazolidinones (II)						
	m.p. °C	% Sulphur		SA*	BS*	m.p. °C	% Sulphur		SA*	BS*	CA**	AN**
		Found	Calcd.				Found	Calcd.				
a	—	—	—	—	+	—	—	—	+	+	100	—
b	230	27.06	27.11	+	2+	172	23.10	23.18	2+	2+	100	100
c	263	24.19	24.06	+	—	165	20.73	20.91	3+	—	50	100
d	300	23.46	23.70	—	+	214	20.43	20.64	+	—	—	—
e	244	22.23	22.47	—	—	175	19.80	19.93	+	+	—	—
f	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	+	—	—	—
g	217	12.86	12.80	—	+	152	11.00	11.08	—	—	100	—
h	232	12.89	12.59	—	—	230	10.61	10.86	+	—	—	—
i	224	12.18	12.07	+	—	247	10.32	10.49	—	—	—	—
j	234	12.46	12.59	—	—	232	10.73	10.86	—	—	—	—
k	—	—	—	+	+	—	—	—	3+	3+	50	50

*SA = *S. aureus*, BS = *B. subtilis*; + = zone size 6-8 mm, 2+ = zone size 9-14 mm, 3+ = zone size 15-20 mm, - = inactive.
**CA = *C. albican*, AN = *A. niger*; The number indicates minimum inhibitory concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

TABLE 2

Compound	Benzylidenethiazolidinones (III)					Dibromides (IV)						
	m.p. °C	%Sulphur		BS**	CA**	m.p. °C	%Bromine		SA**	BS**	CA***	AN***
		Found	Calcd.				Found	Calcd.				
a	—	—	—	+	+	200	35.60	35.71	2+	2+	50	50
b	206	17.38	17.58	—	100	176	30.46	30.53	+	+	100	100
c	193	16.13	16.24	+	—	207	29.73	29.96	+	+	50	100
d	189	16.12	16.04	+	50	196	11.30*	11.46	2+	3+	12.5	50
e	176	15.81	15.72	—	100	210	28.06	28.21	+	+	100	100
f	229	9.30	9.19	—	—	182	31.31	31.49	+	+	100	100
g	185	8.28	8.46	—	—	156	29.63	29.73	—	—	—	—
h	219	8.16	8.35	—	—	168	5.75*	5.89	+	+	—	—
i	158	8.23	8.13	—	—	192	29.07	29.03	—	—	—	—
j	226	8.26	8.35	—	—	165	5.68*	5.89	—	—	—	—
k	176	17.50	17.62	+	100	144	30.27	30.49	3+	2+	12.5	50

*Indicates percentage of sulphur.

**SA = *S. aureus*, BS = *B. subtilis*; + = zone size 6.8 mm, 2+ = zone size 9-14 mm, 3+ = zone size 15-20 mm, — = inactive.

***CA = *C. albican*, AN = *A. niger*; the number indicates minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/ml.

TABLE 3

Compound	Sulphonamido derivatives (V)					Aminomethyl derivatives (VI)							
	m.p. °C	%Nitrogen		SA*	BS*	CA**	m.p. °C	%Sulphur		SA*	BS*	CA**	AN**
		Found	Calcd.					Found	Calcd.				
a	167	27.74	27.92	+	2+	50	—	—	—	+	+	—	—
b	182	22.83	22.95	2+	2+	—	246	19.30	19.21	+	+	—	50
c	191	22.26	21.44	—	—	—	250	17.52	17.63	—	—	—	—
f	206	23.91	23.84	+	+	50	212	10.30	10.09	+	—	—	—
g	210	22.36	22.22	+	+	50	223	9.15	9.22	+	+	—	—
k	178	28.06	28.00	2+	2+	50	214	19.10	19.27	+	+	—	—

*SA = *S. aureus*, BS = *B. subtilis*; + = zone size 6-9, 2+ = zone size 10-14, 3+ = zone size 15-20 mm, — = inactive.

**CA = *C. albican*, AN = *A. niger*; the number indicates minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/ml.

dinone (1.0 g), dimethylamine (0.5 g), paraformaldehyde (1.0 g) and conc. HCl (2 ml) in ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The solvent was distilled off. The gummy residue was kept in contact with ammonia overnight during which it got solidified. It was filtered, washed several times with water and finally recrystallised from DMF, m.p. 174°, yield 0.75 g (60%). (Found: S, 24.75%. $C_8H_{11}N_2S_2O$ requires S, 24.92%).

The analytical data and microbial test results of the sulphonamido derivatives and aminomethyl thiazolidinones are presented in Table 3.

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